

THE IMPORTANCE OF PREVENTING ERRORS IN THE ORGANIZATION OF WRITTEN SPEECH

Okmonova Sevinchoy

Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyoz, Faculty of Turkish Languages, 2nd level student of Uzbek language education in foreign language groups

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8053952>

ANNOTATION: In this article, there are thoughts and comments on the prevention and elimination of errors in the organization of written speech, and practical recommendations are given in the continuation of the article. The special importance of pedagogical education is one of the urgent importance of the issue of training students and young people to become mature and good personnel in all respects is that the formation of written speech in the case of strict adherence to the norms of spelling and methodical language is one of the urgent tasks. .

KEY WORDS: speech errors, morphological-methodical errors, syntactic-methodical errors, logical errors, concept of methodology, repeated use of one word.

The importance of preventing mistakes in the organization of written speech is also evaluated by the level of scientific literacy of students. In addition, the purpose of the organization of written speech in order to prevent factual errors and syntactical and stylistic errors is to get acquainted with the alternative version of words, to provide understanding of logical errors and misunderstandings. "All types of written work conducted are a means of determining literacy and eliminating errors. Therefore, it is necessary to use all types of written work in determining literacy. We make some mistakes knowingly or unknowingly while writing. Such errors are very diverse. Speech errors include wrongly chosen (inappropriate) words, inappropriately structured sentences, incorrect use of morphological forms. Morphological and stylistic errors include errors resulting from the incorrect use of word-form modifiers and word-forming adverbs". [1] In fact, in connection with the correct formation of the written speech, along with the use of orthographically and stylistically correct and alternative words, it is also explained by the fact that the expressed words are stylistically characterized or not. Accordingly, when using a second word instead of one word, in addition to the laws of expressiveness and correctness, it is advisable to use stylistically characterized words in relation to the event being described, and what kind of content and style the text is in. is also represented by explanatory parts.

Working with speech errors and their prevention is one of the most important tools for the prevention of errors in the organization of written speech. Also, in the duration of speech errors, speech errors occur due to the use of parasitic words and speech repetitions. In general, prevention of speech errors and reduction of their impact on speech is good performance. In this regard, the role of school education is great, and the issue of preparing students and young people to become mature personnel in all respects is distinguished by its urgency. "Speech is a means of expressing thoughts, expressed in oral and written form. Thinking happens with the help of nut, thanks to which people communicate with each other. If oral speech reaches the listener through pauses, accents, intonation and sounds, written

speech is a combination of letters and words based on a certain law, punctuation marks, various separations, grammatically clear sentences and pronunciation of sounds. reaches through Another difference between oral speech and written speech is that we hear spoken speech, see and read written speech. Written speech is a complex process that requires a lot of work. Syntactically speaking, written speech is the most complete and perfect speech. This speech is the best way to express our free will. Written speech develops on the basis of oral speech. Oral speech develops by interacting with people in life, imitating them, and does not require special reading and learning from the child. Written speech is a speech intended for visual perception of sounds, words, sentences with the help of letters and symbols, and writing by hand".[2] Errors that occur during the duration of both forms of speech are mainly defined as the inability to use dialect words or alternative forms of words. In most cases, more errors have been observed in the written speech process than in the oral communication style. The reason for this is the fact that the written speech has not developed in a good and meaningful way, and it is expressed by the fact that people's oral communication is transferred to the written form. That is why there are different aspects of oral communication style and written communication style It is understood that it is necessary to strictly follow the principles of evaluation, generalization and comparison. Relying on the expressiveness mentioned above, speech errors can be divided as follows.

1. Lexical - methodological errors;
2. Morphological - methodological errors;
3. Syntactic - methodological errors;
4. Using the same word over and over again.

One of the most alternative ways to prevent stylistic errors from the surface of the use of words is the principle of working with the spiritual entities represented by the words, which is distinguished by the fact that the principle of familiarity with synonyms is also widely used. It should not be forgotten that in order to prevent lexical-methodological errors, it is important to know well the technique of working with the classification of adverbs. In fact, it is explained that mistakes occur in many cases due to the correct and exemplary use of the words explained by the adverbs. Therefore, pedagogues engaged in school education should be aware of the correct use of words used in the expression of dialogue text or any written text that occurs between a speaker or a listener. attention is required.

"Logical fallacies:

1. The word necessary for the depicted event, sometimes the necessary picture, evidence is left out. To understand the reason for such a mistake, it is necessary to observe the mental state of the student at the time of writing the essay.
2. Logical consistency is broken. For example, cotton yarn is made at the factory. A picker picks cotton in a cotton picker. Such logical errors are easily corrected by students in the process of re-reading and analyzing the text. A system for correcting and preventing speech errors will be developed based on the grouping of errors made by students, identification of their types, and the study of the causes of each error: 1) students of speech errors correction in the notebook; 2) working in the classroom on speech errors common to students of the class (15-20 minutes of the lesson will be allocated for this and the checked essay and statement will be analyzed, the students will be able to independently find the error and correct it correction is allowed);

References:

1.

Kurbaniozov Gulmirza, Jalilov Sadaddin. Practical Uzbek language. Nukus "Nur-Turan-Print" 2023

2. Ikromova Ominakhan Elmurod's daughter, Rahimova Charoskhan Odiljonovna. Article "Eliminating deficiencies in the written speech of primary school students" - 2022

3. Muhayyo Zaripovna Abdiyazova, Bahorgul Yusupovna Mametova. Speech errors and ways to eliminate them. Scientific progress -2021

